

LISTENING SKILL. IMPROVING LISTENING SKILL PROFICIENCY

Aziza Hayitboyeva

3rd grade, the faculty of foreign language and literature

Jizzakh State Pedagogical University

Scientific supervisor: **Qurbonova Nasiba**

Abstract: In this article we will discuss listening skill. And, how to improving comprehension on this part of skill. Being able to understand English is the key to speaking it. So prioritise your listening skills. Here’s everything you need to know about learning to understand spoken English, and I am going to write about useful methods that can be beneficial in order to improve your listening skill to some point. Listening is key factor in all conversation cases, the main reason is while communication you should understand the speaker that you are holding conversation. To give good response for their argument understading only way for responder to not put himself in an uncomfortable situation. Here you will get some hacks for improvement of listening proficiency. Sure, some teachers will tell you that you need to speak from day one. They’ll emphasise the importance of interaction with native speakers and the importance of producing language. And as a learner, you probably agree—most of students pay me to tutor them because they want to be able to speak English, not listen to it. Yes, speaking is important. Yes, learning to produce English is part of learning it. But, in my opinion, listening is the most important English skill.

Keywords: listening skill, comprehension, watching, atmosphere, learning interaction, practise, recordings, videos, films.

You can’t have a conversation with someone if you can’t understand what they’re saying. Listening is the first step to being able to have a conversation. Get good at listening, and you’ll set yourself up for being able to have successful conversations. Listening helps you build basic language skills so that when you start speaking, you’re not going to feel like it’s impossible.

This isn't just my opinion, it's one of the fundamental principles of Stephen Krashen, the legendary linguist, Professor Emeritus at the University of Southern California, and someone who certainly knows more about how to effectively learn languages than almost everyone else on the planet.

“The best methods are therefore those that supply 'comprehensible input' in low anxiety situations, containing messages that students really want to hear. These methods do not force early production in the second language, but allow students to produce when they are 'ready', recognizing that improvement comes from supplying communicative and comprehensible input, and not from forcing and correcting production.”

Stephen Krashen, Principles and Practice Second Language Acquisition.

So, we know how important is it to understand Native speakers in their language. But, what kind of steps do we need to take for the great comprehension. Are there any key methods that can assist to comprehend language, you are learning.

Of course, Yes. 1st thing that you have to do adjusting the listening sources to your level.

If you decide to practice and **improve your English listening**, be aware the materials you select are not too challenging for you. It's actually okay to learn just couple of words when listening; you do not have to learn 20+ new words each time you practice listening. Choosing materials which are above your English level is counterproductive – on top of feeling discouraged and frustrated, you will not be able to remember many words long-term. On the other hand, if you choose easier recordings and listening exercises, with just a few new words to learn each time, you will be more satisfied and efficient when learning. But you can't go too easy on yourself, either. Just make sure you understand the majority of the recording and that you're adding several new words to your vocabulary lists after each, listening exercise. You can also increase the difficulty of your exercise by speeding up the recordings you are practicing with. If you are not sure what kind of speed is okay for you, experiment – on most apps, you can slow down or speed up a recording easily. Try doing that!

Most of you I think usually stuck at the same level in your listening section, although there are many ways to improve it, for me watching TV series always stand out rather than others. Just watching TV series not only help you improve your listening skill but also it can increase your knowledge about culture of English speaking countries and also your oval vocabulary and so on. Take a sitcom which is in your taste. And try to watch one or two series of it for yourself.

Now I will give you some more methods I did before passing my exam to increase my score on listening.

Listen and watch what you like more. As an example of me, if I have free time I just listen to music and sing a song. And sometimes I listen some podcasts especially interesting ones on BBC learning English or just listen section 3 and 4 to improve my comprehension. As you know these sections are very important ones and if don't have enough comprehension you will miss answers while listening test. So, for watching, I really into TV programmes on You tube. And my favourite is TONIGHT WITH JIM FALLON. It is very interesting and informative. Try to watch your preferred programme or other kind of things just like cooking or sport reviews in English. I am sure you will see improvement in a short period of time.

As I mentioned sitcoms, TV series are much more beneficial than films because you can know what will happen in films and most of people don't pay attention the words they use but for action. So, watching them often cannot give you some knowledge on learning process. However, when it comes to Tv series in order to understand the meaning of it you should have good command of language. And this one is the most important one for us. I watched one sitcom that helped me a lot. Although it contains some scenes which is not suitable to our culture. But the main purpose of you to get good sides of it. The name of Sitcom is VICTORIUS about college students in AMERICA. With learning good language features you also learn more about culture of America.

Since English is a language which is spoken worldwide by people of many nations, there are numerous English accents. What kind of accent you speak yourself depends on where you live, what is your native language, when did you start learning

English, what kind of materials do you use to learn English, and so on. Therefore, if you want to be proficient in English or live in an English-speaking country, you need to get used to various different accents.

A great way to familiarize yourself with a bunch of accents is to watch a TED talk. TED talks conferences are being organized worldwide, making it possible for everyone to participate in it. Many speakers want to connect with an English-speaking audience, therefore they choose to speak English. You can try typing on YouTube “TED talk + country” to find a video from any particular country you like. The more you practice, the better you get – that’s a well-known fact. If you want to **improve your listening skills in English** and take them to the next level, practice as much as possible. Having said that, your study sessions shouldn’t last too long. As listening requires a lot of focus, it is very difficult, if not impossible, to keep up with English listening practice for an hour or two. What’s more important is frequency. Try to listen to English speech every day for at least 10-30 minutes, depending how much time is on your hands. You can do that on your way to work or to school, you also try doing it when cleaning or doing other household chores. If possible, try to re-listen later and write down all the new words and grammar you hear.